

ISic3343

I.Sicily inscription 3343

Language

Possibly Messapic

Type

terminus

Material

sandstone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Canicattini Bagni

Provenance

contr. Bibia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Canicattini Bagni

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 645588

Bibliography

Manganaro Perrone, G. 2008. Un cippo fondiario in Messapico da Canicattini Bagni (territorio siracusano). *Epigraphica*. 70: 9-20.

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